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Forage Productivity of Maize-Legume Residues Under Different Cropping Systems

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ABSTRACT

The study was designed to evaluate the effect of intercropping on forage biomass and crude protein yield of maize-legume mixtures. The experiment was conducted during the early and late cropping seasons of 2024 in the Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Delta State University, Abraka. The experiment consisted of 9 treatments, namely continuous cropping (sole maize M, soybean S, blackbean B), rotation (S-B, S-M and B-M) and rotation of intercrop (S/B-S/B, S/M-S/M, B/M-B/M). The 9 treatments were replicated 3 times and laid out in a randomized complete block design. Data were collected on fresh forage yield (FBY), dry matter yield (DMY) and crude protein yield (CPY). Results showed that FBY and DMY of maize, soybean and blackbean were significantly higher in sole cropping than intercrops. Maize mixed with legumes possessed significantly higher CPY than sole crop. Yield gain in terms of DMER and LER showed advantage in all intercrops. In general LER was higher in soybean-blackbean intercrop than maize based intercrops. CPY of all the crops was higher in the late season cropping compared to early season.

Keywords: dry matter yield, maize, legumes, LER

INTRODUCTION

Livestock production holds the key to animal protein source to majority of the Nigerian populace. Successful livestock production is achieved through maximizing productivity of cereals and legumes which constitute the major source of energy and protein for livestock (Yilmaz et al., 2015). Cereal-legume intercropping system is a widely proposed strategy to achieve a sustainable food and forage production system [Ayele, 2020) to replenish the food and feed gaps especially among farmers in developing countries with limited resources and access to agricultural inputs (Yang, et al., 2018). Maize is one of the most important cereal crops that could substantially be used to improve livestock feeding. Maize-legume intercropping is also known to be one of the practices in the agricultural production system that could increase forage quality and quantity and decrease requirements for protein supplements in livestock feeds (Belel and Amina, 2022).

Maize (*Zea mays* L.), soybean (*Glycine max*) and blackbean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L) are vital field food crops in Nigeria. The present study was designed to evaluate the effect of intercropping on forage biomass and crude protein yield of maize-legume mixtures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted during the early (April to July) and late (August to November) cropping seasons of 2024 in the Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Delta State University, Abraka. The experiment consisted of 9 treatments, namely continuous cropping (sole maize, soybean, blackbean), rotation (soybean-blackbean, soybean-maize and blackbean-maize) and rotation of intercrop

(soybean/blackbean-soybean/blackbean, soybean/maize-soybean/maize, blackbean/maize-blackbean/maize). The 9 treatments were replicated 3 times and laid in a randomized complete block design. Maize was established on plots at a spacing of 90cm x 30cm, while both soybean and blackbean were sown at 60 cm x 45cm. All intercrops were planted in 1:1 ratio. Crop varieties used for experiment were: maize (cv. TZSR-Y), soybean (cv. TGX 2004-10F) and black bean (cv. Dangora).

At maturity, maize, soybean and blackbean forage within inner 1m² were harvested 5cm above ground level for determination of fresh biomass yield and further evaluation of nitrogen content. A random sample of 500g of each crop species was collected from each plot and oven dried at 70°C to constant weight to obtain the dry matter yield. The dried samples of forages were milled using a mill and passed through 1-2mm sieve, for further analysis. The nitrogen (N) content was analyzed using the Kjeldahl procedure (AOAC, 2012), then crude protein (CP) was calculated as product of N and 6.25. The forage yield, dry matter and crude protein yield obtained were converted into kg ha⁻¹.

Land equivalent ratio (LER) was determined as the sum of the fractions of the fresh biological yield (kg ha⁻¹) of soybean and maize intercrops relative to their sole crop yields, where LER:

$$LER = Y_{ji}/Y_{jj} + Y_{ij}/Y_{ii}$$

where, Y_{ji} is yield of soybean “j” intercropped with maize “i”, Y_{ii} is pure stand yield of soybean “i”, Y_{ij} is yield of maize “i” intercropped with soybean “j”, Y_{ii} is pure stand yield of maize “i”.

Dry matter equivalent ratio (DMER) was estimated as the sum of the DM yield of the companion crop relative to the DM yield of the sole crop (DeWit et al., 1965) using the equation below:

$$DMER = DMY_{ji} + DMY_{ij}/DMY_{ii}$$

Where DMY_{ji} = dry matter yield of maize in intercrop with soybean or blackbean

DMY_{ij} = dry matter yield of soybean or blackbean in intercrop with maize

DMY_{ii} = dry matter yield of sole maize, soybean or blackbean

For a rotation, it would be the sum of the LER and DMER over the entire cycle.

Data obtained were subjected to two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) appropriate for randomized complete block designs. Significant means were separated using the least significant difference

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fresh Biomass Yield (FBY)

During the early cropping, the fresh biomass yield (FBY) of maize intercropped with soybean and blackbean were 10348.7 kg ha⁻¹ and 10158.3 kg ha⁻¹ respectively (Table 1). Sole maize had a better FBY (11861.5 kg ha⁻¹). FBY of soybean ranged from 8106.5 to 7836.3 kg ha⁻¹ in intercropped rotations and significantly lower than sole soybean ranging from 9006.8 to 9105.0 kg ha⁻¹. FBY of sole blackbean (7896.1 to 7991.8 kg ha⁻¹) was significantly higher than intercrops which ranged from 7188.4 to 7388.7 kg ha⁻¹. Similar trend was observed in late cropping with sole maize, soybean and blackbean performing better than the intercrops in FBY (Table 2).

Dry matter Yield (DMY)

The results in Table 1, shows that the dry matter yield (DMY) of early cropped sole maize (4102.6 kg ha⁻¹) was significantly higher than maize intercropped with soybean (3197.7 kg ha⁻¹) and blackbean (3178.5 kg ha⁻¹). In the late cropping, sole cropped DMY in both continuous and rotation cropping showed no significant difference and ranged from 2817.9 to 2822.8 kg ha⁻¹. Soybean DMY in sole cropping and rotations ranged from 2818.8 to 2822.8 kg ha⁻¹, indicating significantly higher values than intercrops with blackbean (2518.7 kg ha⁻¹) and maize (2436.3 kg ha⁻¹). The late cropped soybean also showed significantly reduced DMY of intercrops with maize (2436.3 kg ha⁻¹) and blackbean (2518.7 kg ha⁻¹) compared to sole cropped soybean ranging from 2817.9 to 2822.8 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 2). DMY of sole cropped blackbean in continuous and rotation cropping plots ranged from 2570.8 to 2584.8 kg ha⁻¹; and was significantly higher than intercrop with soybean (2167.3 kg ha⁻¹) and maize (2009.7 kg ha⁻¹). Late cropped blackbean DMY ranged from 2462.8 kg ha⁻¹ (continuous) to 2485.3 kg ha⁻¹ (rotation with soybean). These values were significantly higher than DMY of intercrop with 2167.3 kg ha⁻¹ (S/B) and 2133.5 kg ha⁻¹ (B/M).

Crude Protein Yield (CPY)

Maize mixed with legumes possessed better CPY than sole crop. CPY values ranging from 251.5 kg ha⁻¹ (S/M) to 257.0 kg ha⁻¹ (B/M), while sole maize showed CPY of 241.4 kg ha⁻¹. Soybean in intercrop showed significantly lower CPY with maize 404.60 kg ha⁻¹ and blackbean 412.80 kg ha⁻¹, relative to sole crop 473.50 kg ha⁻¹.(continuous) and rotation (469.8 to 474,2 kg ha⁻¹). CPY of blackbean ranged from 425.1 to 476.7 kg ha⁻¹ in early cropping and 476.7 kg ha⁻¹. Intercropping significantly reduced CPY in blackbean and was lower with intercropping with maize. On the average CPY of all the crops was higher in the late season cropping compared to early season.

Table 1: .Fresh biomass, dry matter and crude protein yield of maize, soybean and blackbean early cropping season of 2024

Sole cropping	Fresh Biomass Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Dry matter Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Crude Protein Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)		
	Maize	Soybean	Black bean	Maize	Soybean	Black bean	Maize	Soybean	Black bean
Sole cropping									
M	11861.5			4102.6			241.4		
S		9105.0			2818.8			473.5	
B			7991.8			2572.7			476.7
Rotation									
S-B		9150.1			2822.8	2584.8		474,2	467.9
S-M		9066.6			2817.9			469.8	470.5
B-M			7896.1			2570.8			
Rotation of intercrop									
S/B-S/B		8106.5	7388.7		2518.7	2167.3		412.8	456.5
S/M-S/M	10348.7	7836.3		3197.7	2436.3		251.5	404.6	
B/M-B/M	10158.3		7188.4	3178.5		2009.7	257.0		425.1
LSD (5%)	13.9	48.7	34.1	22.7	30.7	23.9	1.9	9.7	3.9

M-Maize, S-soybean, B-Blackbean

Table 2: Fresh biomass, dry matter and crude protein yield of maize, soybean and blackbean late cropping season of 2024

Cropping system	Fresh Biomass Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Dry matter Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Crude Protein Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)		
	Maize	Soybean	Black bean	Maize	Soybean	Black bean	Maize	Soybean	Black bean
Sole cropping									
M	10852.6			3776.7			252.4		
S		8838.6			2708.8			483.6	
B			7569.3			2462.8			480.6
Sole crop									
Rotation									
S-B			7485.2			2485.3			
S-M	9005.6			3805.9			254.2		
B-M	9089.1			3796.8			258.6		
Intercrop									
Rotation									
S/B-S/B		8207.7	6992.5		2483.1	2286.3		452.8	465,3
S/M-S/M	9856,7	7661.3		2427.1	2419.8		260.5	460.3	
B/M-B/M	9678.3		6105.3	2129.6		2133.5	263.4		470.7
LSD (5%)	29.4	31.0	41.9	33.8	44	19.8	2.8	5.3	3.9

M-Maize, S-soybean, B-Blackbean

Land Use Efficiency and Yield Advantage

Data of LER, presented in Table 3 indicated fresh residues from maize, soybean and blackbean during late cropping showed a more pronounced effect on land use resulting in a clear yield advantage of 1.72 (S/B) and 1.61 (S/M) and clear higher values at the end of the rotation cycle, 3.42 (S/B), 3.14 (S/M) and 2.91 (B/M). In general LER was higher in soybean-blackbean intercrop than maize based intercrops. Ascertaining the yield gain in terms of DMER (Table 3), residues of maize, soybean and blackbean showed advantage in all intercrops with highest and lowest values recorded in soybean-blackbean (1.66-early, 1.76-late) and blackbean-maize (1.26-early, 1.13-late) respectively. The rotation cycle also recorded highest LER value in soybean-blackbean (3.42), while soybean-maize (2.65) had the least value.

Table 3 Land equivalent ratio (LER), and dry matter equivalent ratio (DMER) of maize, soybean and blackbean intercropping

Cropping system	LER			DMER		
	Early	Late	Rotation cycle	Early	Late	Rotation cycle
S/B-S/B	1.70	1.72	3.42	1.66	1.76	3.42
S/M-S/M	1.53	1.61	3.14	1.37	1.28	2.65
B/M-B/M	1.46	1.45	2.91	1.26	1.13	2.49

In consonance with the results of this study, the differences in fodder yield of soybean or blackbean intercropped with maize can be linked to the stage of maturity of the maize companion crop. Cereals are generally characterized as vigorous plants with higher growth rates than legumes, thus, they often reduce the growth of associated legumes when intercropped together. Other related reports (Liu et al., 2016) also indicated that intercropping enhanced the growth of maize, with consequent negative effect on the growth of the accompanying soybean.

Sowing maize with legume component reduced yield of the intercrop compared to sole crops, probably because of the high competition associated with sowing both crops together at the same time which significantly suppressed the ability of the soybean or blackbean plant to convert the photosynthetic assimilates into the economic fodder component. The high shading of the fast-growing fodder maize crop may have also reduced the light intensity reaching the lower soybean or blackbean canopy, which resulted in plants with reduced biomass yield.

Legume contributions to maize in mixtures are important sources of silage material in livestock husbandry (Kizilsimsek *et al.*, 2020). Forage value is not only assessed by its dry matter, but also by its protein content (Sadeghpour *et al.* 2013). In this study, the mixtures possessed higher CP contents and yields, this is agreement with other researchers (Altinok *et al.*, 2005; Belel and Amina, 2022) who also reported that sowing techniques are beneficial for silage CP content and yield. The CPY of the late season was higher than the early season. Széles *et al.* (2018) noted that higher protein content sometimes observed in dry conditions are due to reduced photosynthesis, leading to a better balance of protein and starch, while wet conditions can leach nitrogen from the soil, decreasing protein concentration.

The achieved yield gain in terms of high LER and DMER values could be attributed to the complementarity in utilization of below and above-ground resources and farming inputs between the intercrop component crops (Salama *et al.* 2021). The yield gain of the intercropping system compared to sole cropping of both crops, can be better described with LER whether fodder crop is cultivated for green feeding and with DMER when cropped for silage production.

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